

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE CONDITION OF THE HARD TISSUES OF THE TOOTH AND PERIODONTAL IN PATIENTS WITH HIV-INFECTED

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Abstract

The article presents data on the study of the state of tissues and organs of the oral cavity of 67 HIV-infected patients. A significantly higher prevalence of caries and its complications, as well as periodontal diseases in these patients was revealed in comparison with immunocompetent individuals, it was also noted that, against the background of immunosuppression, destructive changes in the hard tissues of the teeth were also noted, which led to the formation of a large number of missing and destroyed teeth as a result of complicated caries, which contributed to overload and violation of the trophic periodontal. Also, the results of an immunological study of oral fluid confirmed a significant inhibition of local immunity factors in people living with HIV.

Keywords: dentistry, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), HIV infection, periodontitis, gingivitis, oral mucosa.

Relevance. It is known that the transmission of HIV infection is carried out by the following mechanisms - natural, vertical and artificial at the same time, the ways of implementing the mechanisms of transmission of the pathogen can be sexual, transplacental, parenteral [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Moreover, in dentistry, most manipulations are invasive, which makes it quite the real is the artificial mechanism of HIV transmission, and the leading pathway is parenteral. Knowledge of the symptoms of oral cavity lesion (PR) at various stages of the clinical course of HIV infection is necessary for a dentist. The presence of these symptoms, along with other signs indicating a possible immunodeficiency, can help clarify the diagnosis [11, 13, 14, 18].

According to the clinic, PR lesions accompany HIV infection from the second clinical stage of the infectious process [6, 7]. The occurrence of diseases of the oral cavity (RP) is most often associated with the development of so-called secondary diseases – opportunistic infections and tumors inherent in immunodeficiency of the body, such as candidiasis PR, including angular cheilitis, "hairy" leukoplakia, HIV gingivitis, HIV periodontitis, recurrent herpetic stomatitis, Kaposi's sarcoma, lymphoma not Hodgkin and others [2, 3, 4, 15]. It is also known that the manifestations of HIV infection in PR are key indicators of the development of the disease [16, 17]. Therefore, the dentist should take into account the following: in the case when the HIV status of the patient is not known, the lesions of the PR may indicate the presence of HIV infection; in the case of patients with an established diagnosis of "HIV infection" who do not show symptoms of the disease and, therefore, do not take antiretroviral drugs (ARVP), the presence of lesions PR can signal the development of the disease. It is shown that the patient is referred to an infectious disease doctor to measure the level of viral load (VN) and determine the immune status; - in the event that patients take ARVP, the presence of lesions of the PR may indicate the ineffectiveness of

treatment. It is shown that the patient is referred to an infectious disease doctor in order to correct ART [5]. Pathology of the tissue and organs of the PR, including pathology of the hard tissues of the teeth, periodontal tissues and defects of the dentition in HIV-infected patients lead to a significant decrease in the quality of life (QOL) of patients [12, 17].

Today, experts point to the need to improve dental care, which is included in the recommendations in many countries of the world. It is necessary to register the clinical picture identified by the dentist in the patient's card. Dentists serving patients with HIV infection should know the stage of the disease, the level of CD4 lymphocytes and VN in the blood, register their recommendations in writing, know the basics of medical and social counseling, and know the peculiarities of patients' psychosomatics [19]. A number of scientists have developed an algorithm for providing outpatient care, universal at any stage of HIV infection, in order to optimize the work of a dentist providing therapeutic and preventive care to HIV-infected patients [13]. Together with other scientists [2, 3, 4], recommendations were prepared, including issues of HIV prevention in dental practice. However, an analysis of the literature shows that the issues of providing dental care to people living with HIV continue to remain little or almost unexplored. Meanwhile, scientific research in this area would make it possible to develop a tactic approach to assessing the condition of PR in HIV-infected patients and the specifics of providing dental, including orthopedic care, starting with addressing the issues of indications and contraindications to dental prosthetics, the timing of treatment, the choice of methods, designs, materials for the manufacture of dentures, and also features of the care of PR, prostheses and tissues of the prosthetic bed. In this regard, the expediency of disclosing the issue covering these diseases is beyond doubt.

The purpose of the study. The study of the state of tissues and organs of PR for the development of optimal methods and approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of dental pathologies of HIV-infected patients.

Materials and methods. This work was carried out at the Department of "Therapeutic Dentistry" of the Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina together with the regional branches of the Republican AIDS Control Center. For the period from 2020 to 2023. 67 patients with HIV infection were examined, including n=47 of them were divided into 2 groups for further comparison, depending on the condition of the PR and the planned treatment methods: 1-control group (C/D) - 23 patients (11 patients who have removable partial prostheses and 12 patients who need in prosthetics partially-removable and full removable dentures; 2 experimental group – 24 patients, also having, of varying degrees, defects of dentition. In addition to gender, patients were divided into age groups: 18-25 years - 34.7%, 26-34 years -54.3%, 35-44 years -11.0% of the total number of examined. In order to compare the state of immunological parameters of PR/G, 14 patients with periodontal diseases of moderate severity served.

When collecting anamnestic data, concomitant and transferred diseases, the duration of the underlying disease were found out, the allergological history, profession, the presence of bad habits were clarified, to what extent the patient owns and how individual hygienic care for the PR is carried out. Visual dental examination of the PR was carried out with the help of disposable dental instruments in natural light. The study began with an examination of the red border of the lips, cheeks, soft and hard palate, bottom of the mouth, gums, tongue. The condition of the hard tissues of the teeth, the presence of fillings, inlays, crowns and prostheses were taken into account, the presence of dentition defects, their topography and extent, the presence of dentition defects, the shape of dental arches, including the type of bite were determined. Partial defects in the dentition were assessed according to the Kennedy classification. The condition of the salivary glands was also determined, all of the above indicators were recorded in a special card of a patient with HIV infection developed for this study.

Clinical methods for the study of the dental status of patients were carried out using standard methods; the prevalence of caries was determined by the percentage of persons with carious (K), filled (N) and removed (Y) teeth (CP); the state of hygiene of the PR was assessed using the Green-Vermillion hygiene index (ONI-s, 1969); periodontal index (PI according to the Russel method of 1956); pronounced destruction of periodontal tissues according to Muhlleman-Cowell (Muhlleman, 1971, Cowell, 1975); the intensity of gingival bleeding was determined (ICD method); The need for treatment of periodontal diseases was assessed using the CPITN index [16].

With the help of a stomatoscopic examination, the dynamic functional feature of the state of the oral mucosa (SOPR) and microcirculation in a living organism

was evaluated. Intravital microangiography or stomatoscopy was used. Stomatoscopy was started from unaffected areas, then switched to the affected mucosa. The study of the SOPR under high magnification made it possible to assess the degree of translucency of the underlying vessels, their caliber, density, uniformity of color, the number of connective-woven papillae, the presence of keratosis, swelling phenomena, the appearance of shades of cyanosis, desolation of vessels, pallor of the SOPR, which made it possible to clarify the diagnosis and nature of the course of pathology of the SOPR and periodontal.

Using the gnathodinamometer device [1], the functional state of periodontal tissues was evaluated [8, 9], two types of radiography (R) - SD-1 or SD-2 and panoramic on the orthopantomograph "Ortophos-3" were also used for the study.

With dental research methods in the same groups of sick people infected with HIV, we conducted immunological studies of oral fluid (RS); collected RS in sterile tubes in the morning (at 9-10 o'clock), after meals and in the laboratory determined the concentration of slg A, lysozyme concentration by immunoturbidimetry (Boehringer Mannheim), in the method of J. Mancini (1965) is the basis of the definition of SIDA. The activity of lysozyme in saliva was determined using the method proposed by Aliyev Sh.R. (1994), for this purpose, saliva sampling was carried out on an empty stomach in sterile test tubes and thoroughly soaked them in saliva, then these discs were placed on the surface of nutrient agar (Diffco agar) in Petri dishes sown with a lawn of a daily Micr culture. *Lygodeikticus* (strain 2665 GKI named after L.A. Tarasevich). The crops were incubated at a temperature of 37 ° C, the activity of lysozyme in saliva was determined by the method of diffusion in agar [10].

The obtained data were processed using Microsoft Excel and Statistica-6 computer programs. Statistical processing of the results of the study was carried out by calculating the arithmetic mean (M), the standard deviation and the average error of the indicator (m). The comparison of indicators between groups was carried out using the student's t-test. The differences between the groups were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. According to the results of clinical observations, we revealed a significantly higher prevalence of caries and its complications in HIV-infected patients compared with immunocompetent individuals (100% vs. 80% respectively). The caries intensity index was in HIV-infected patients in C/ G; CPU = 18.6 ± 0.5 , in patients in the experimental group - CPU = 19.2 ± 0.8 , which is considered very high according to WHO gradation. According to our data, the structure of the CPI index in people with HIV in A/G consisted of the following indicators: "K"-56%, "P" - 12%, "Y"- 32%; the intensity of caries in HIV-infected people in group 2 "K" - 61%, "P" - 11%, "Y" - 28%. The need for caries treatment in both groups 1 and 2 was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) than in the comparison group, where the value of the CPI index was 9.8 ± 0.4 . The number of carious teeth in women was lower than in men (by 13% in the group of patients with HIV in C/G and on 8% -

in the experimental group); there was a tendency to increase the number of filled and removed teeth compared to men.

In the HIV-infected patients examined by us in group 1, the following inflammatory periodontal diseases were detected: gingivitis, including catarrhal - in 56.8% of patients. Periodontitis was observed in 18% of patients. A mild form of periodontal inflammation in HIV patients in group 1 was detected in 30.4% of pa-

tients, with a PI of 0.93 ± 0.25 . Periodontitis of moderate severity (PI 1.89 ± 0.21) with pronounced destruction, confirmed by R-ski, was observed in 52.2% of patients. Severe periodontitis was noted in 17.4% of the total number of patients with periodontitis. PI in these cases was 2.41 ± 0.26 . The average value of PI in this group of patients was 1.74 ± 0.29 . The depth of clinical pockets reached an average of 5.8 mm, which corresponds to 3 points on the CPITN scale.

Fig. 1. A. The state of the vestibule of PR **B.** Palate in a patient with HIV.

Inflammatory periodontal diseases (IPD) in HIV patients in group 2 were presented as follows: gingivitis, including catarrhal, was observed in 61.4% of patients (Fig. 2), ulcerative necrotic - in 6.3% of the examined (Fig. No. 4.). A mild form of periodontal inflammation was noted in 27.5% of patients, PI was

0.98 ± 0.27 . Periodontitis of moderate severity (PI - 2.1 ± 0.24) was observed in 52.3% of the examined. Severe periodontitis was noted by us in 20.2% of cases when the PI value was 2.8 ± 0.24 . The average value of the PI index was fixed at 1.96 ± 0.23 .

Fig. 2. A. Catarrhal gingivitis. **B.** Ulcerative-necrotic gingivitis in patients with HIV.

An objective examination of the gums revealed a swollen, brightly colored desquamated gingival margin with a cyanotic tinge, slightly bleeding during probing. Periodontal pockets were with abundant purulent-bloody discharge and, often, with juicy granulations. The teeth were covered with a plentiful soft plaque, there were supra- and subgingival dental stones. The weighted average value of ONY-y PR in HIV-infected patients in C/G was 2.64027, in patients with HIV in

the experimental group 2 - 70.24. One of the most sensitive methods for assessing the condition of the gums is a probe test in the majority (98.2%) of the examined HIV-infected patients had bleeding of varying severity (Fig. No. 3). The data of the study of the intensity of periodontal diseases are reflected in Table No. 1. Thus, there were no statistically significant differences in clinical indicators of dental health in the tested groups of patients.

Table 1.

Indicators of periodontal pathology in patients with HIV infection according to the CPITN index.

Indicators of periodontal pathology					
Examined patients	Intensity (segment)	Intact periodontal	Bleeding	Dental deposits	Clinical. pockets
HIV 1 gr.	4,32±0,08	-	2,32±0,04	1,73±0,07	1,58±0,02
HIV 2 gr.	4,5±0,04	-	2,44±0,08	1,82±0,19	1,56±0,16

The intensity of IOP in the groups of HIV-infected patients was high, which is primarily due to severe immunodeficiency. Against the background of immunosuppression, destructive changes in the hard tissues of the teeth were also noted, which led to the formation of a large number of missing and destroyed teeth as a result of complicated caries, and this, in turn, contributed to overload and disruption of periodontal trophic.

The study of the factors that form the specific and nonspecific resistance of RP in HIV-infected patients allowed us to obtain quantitative characteristics of the main factors of RP immunity. In patients in both groups 1 and 2, an imbalance of local immunity indicators was determined in the form of a decrease in the titer of sIgA and the level of lysozyme.

Table 2.

Results of immunological studies of oral fluid of HIV-infected patients before treatment

Indicators	Healthy Group	HIV-1 gr.	HIV-2 gr.
Titer S Ig A, g/l	2,15±0,7	1,42±0,2**	1,24±0,08**
Lysozyme level, mg %	18,4±0,9	10,6±0,8**	11,2±0,5**

Note: * - $p < 0.05$, - $p < 0.01$, * - $p < 0.001$ the reliability of the results in relation to the data of healthy

Analyzing the results of the study in Table No. 2, it can be noted that HIV-infected patients in both groups 1 and 2 had a clear tendency to decrease the activity of the local immunity system compared with the data of the C/G. Thus, the igg titer in patients with HIV in group 1 was 1.42 ± 0.2 g/l, i.e. decreased by > 1.5 times compared to the data of immunocompetent individuals. In the 2 experimental group, the sIg A level was 1.24 ± 0.08 g/l. A similar pattern was observed with respect to lysozyme.

The data obtained indicate a significant decrease in the indicators of local immunity in HIV-infected individuals, which is explained by the pronounced immunosuppression observed in patients with HIV. The revealed patterns may indicate both the strain of antimicrobial protection systems in PR in HIV-infected SOPR.

Discussion. Thus, based on the results of our clinical observations, it can be concluded that the prevalence and intensity of caries in patients with HIV are quite high. In the HIV-infected patients examined by us in 1- gr., revealed; catarrhal gingivitis - in 56.8%; periodontitis - in 18%; mild periodontal inflammation in - 30.4%; PI at the same time was - 0.93, also, with moderate periodontitis (PI- 1.89) with pronounced destruction, confirmed by R-ci, observed in -52.2% of patients. The depth of clinical pockets reached an average of 5.8 mm, ONI-s in patients with HIV in the 2nd C/G - 2.7 ± 0.24 . It was also noted that the condition of the gums - that the majority (98.2%) of the examined HIV-infected patients had bleeding of varying severity. It can be concluded that, against the background of immunosuppression, destructive changes were also noted in the hard tissues of the teeth, which led to the formation of a large number of missing and destroyed teeth as a result of complicated caries, and this, in turn, contributed to overload and disruption of periodontal trophism.

Also, in HIV-infected patients with the help of a stomatoscope, foci of keratinization of CO were detected, stagnant changes in the SOPR with the appearance of small and large-bumpy relief areas. The vascular pattern FROM the soft palate of idna PR, as a rule, was small-caliber, translucent on a general pale-jaundiced background.

PR lesions in HIV-infected patients were characterized by an "aggressive", recurrent nature of the course. The analysis of the results of gnathodynamometric studies convincingly indicates a sharp decrease in the functional state of the periodontal and a high loss of its ability to compensate for functional and structural disorders. Leveling of gnathodynamometry indicators on various groups of teeth indicates a decrease in the functional state of the periodontal.

The specificity of the R-th picture in HIV-infected patients consisted in the generalized nature of the lesion, a combination of horizontal and vertical atrophy of the jaw bone tissue, the formation of large bone pockets, dystrophy of the alveolar process with resorption of the interdental septa, irregular destruction of bone tissue and the supporting and retaining apparatus of the tooth. All changes in the bone tissue were dystrophic in nature. The conducted studies allowed us to obtain quantitative characteristics of the main factors of immunity of patients with HIV infection. In patients in both groups 1 and 2, an imbalance of local immunity indicators was determined in the form of a decrease in the S IgA titer and lysozyme level.

Conclusions:

1. The dental profile of patients with HIV is characterized by high prevalence (100%) and intensity of dental caries (mean CPU= 18.9 ± 0.65), inflammatory periodontal diseases (cf. PI= 1.85 ± 0.26) with a high need for periodontal treatment (cf. CPITN - 4.41 ± 0.06) and poor ONI-s PR (ONI-s - 2.67 ± 0.25).

2. During the stomatoscopic examination of the SOPR, the most pronounced changes are observed in

the area of free and attached gums, which indicates the presence of severe inflammatory periodontal diseases in HIV-infected patients.

3. According to the results of gnathodynamometry, periodontal endurance to horizontal and vertical loads in HIV-infected patients is significantly reduced compared to the data of immunocompetent individuals ($p < 0.05$). Also, the specificity of the R-th picture in HIV-infected patients is the generalized nature of the lesion, a combination of horizontal and vertical atrophy of the bone tissue, dystrophy of the alveolar process with resorption of the interdental septa.

5. The immunological study of RV showed a significant suppression (by 1.5 or more times) of local immunity factors in people living with HIV.

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